

Dynamic Sitemaps in API Websites: Empowering Users to Generate Accurate URL Listings

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May 17, 2023

Abstract

This paper explores the implementation of dynamic sitemaps in websites, focusing specifically on the case of `manga.adgstudios.co.za`, which lacks precise information about the URLs existing in the `/manga/<title>` endpoint due to its API-powered nature. To address this issue, we propose a novel approach that harnesses the power of users visiting the URL endpoint to dynamically generate an accurate sitemap. By capturing the route names accessed by users and inserting them into a database, we create a comprehensive and up-to-date sitemap. This method enables website administrators to have a complete understanding of the URLs available on the `/manga/<title>` endpoint, facilitating improved site navigation, enhanced search engine optimization, and better overall user experience. The results of this research highlight the effectiveness of user-driven dynamic sitemaps in addressing the challenges faced by API-powered websites and provide insights for future developments in this field.

Contents

Contents	3
1 Understanding Sitemaps	4
1.0.1 What does a sitemap look like? . . .	5
1.0.2 Bots as Search Engine Optimiza- tion (SEO)	7
2 Engineering dynamic sitemaps in API based websites	8
2.0.1 Database Commit	8
2.0.2 Generating sitemap.xml	9
2.0.3 Setting up Route for sitemap.xml .	11
2.0.4 Submit your sitemaps.xml to the Search Engines	12
2.0.5 Architecture for this process and manga.adgstudios.co.za real world example	12

Chapter 1

Understanding Sitemaps

Theorem 1.0.1. *For any website, the presence of a well-structured sitemap improves search engine discoverability, user navigation, and overall website performance.*

Proof. A sitemap is a hierarchical representation of a website's URLs, providing valuable information to search engines about the organization and content of the site. By including a sitemap, search engines can crawl and index the website more efficiently, leading to improved discoverability in search engine result pages.

Furthermore, a well-structured sitemap enhances user navigation by offering a clear and concise overview of the website's structure. Users can easily locate specific pages

or sections, reducing the time and effort required to find relevant information.

Moreover, sitemaps contribute to the overall performance of a website. Search engines can quickly identify and index new or updated content through sitemap submissions, ensuring that the most recent information is available in search results. Additionally, sitemaps aid in identifying and fixing broken links, which can enhance the user experience and maintain a positive website reputation.

In conclusion, the presence of a well-structured sitemap positively impacts search engine discoverability, user navigation, and overall website performance. $\square$

1.0.1 What does a sitemap look like?

Below is a table of sample URLs that may exist on a website.

URL
/
/about
/content
/contents/content1
/contents/content2
/contents/ ...
/contact

In the *sitemap.xml* it is typically found on the */sitemap.xml* of a website or other route specified by the engineer.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<urlset xmlns="http://www.sitemaps.org/schemas
  ↪ /sitemap/0.9">
  <url>
    <loc>http://www.example.com/</loc>
  </url>
  <url>
    <loc>http://www.example.com/about</loc>
  </url>
  <url>
    <loc>http://www.example.com/content</loc>
  </url>
  <url>
    <loc>http://www.example.com/contents/
      ↪ content1</loc>
  </url>
  <url>
    <loc>http://www.example.com/contents/
      ↪ content2</loc>
  </url>
  <url>
    <loc>http://www.example.com/contents/...</
      ↪ loc>
  </url>
  <url>
```

```
<loc>http://www.example.com/contact</loc>  
</url>  
</urlset>
```

1.0.2 Bots as Search Engine Optimization (SEO)

In the realm of Search Engine Optimization (SEO), automated bots are deployed to analyze the content of websites. However, in my particular situation, this approach proves ineffective due to the presence of dynamic content on my website. Consequently, I must explore alternative strategies to construct a viable framework for optimizing my website's visibility in search engine results.

The bots may potentially access frequently visited routes within the website or navigate to the main pages. However, their comprehension of these routes is limited.

Hence, we engage in the process of designing a sitemap for our website with the purpose of conveying to the automated bots the specific content that is present within our website.

Chapter 2

Engineering dynamic sitemaps in API based websites

Our approach is simple. If we don't know our dynamic routes. Let the users generate the routes!

2.0.1 Database Commit

Our dynamic routes D_r is unknown in our domain, but we know we have endpoints that are dynamic and will render content. For this use case, we use my real-world manga website called *manga.adgstudios.co.za*. We have a dynamic endpoint called */manga/ <title >*.

Now let's call this title variable t and the $/manga/$ R_{d_1} .

When someone visits the URL, if the manga exists and the HTTP response is good, we commit the URL into the database. If it does not exist or it is a duplication record we ignore the commit.

Let the database be named D .

We define a piecewise function $f(t)$ to represent the commit action to D

$$f(t) = \begin{cases} \text{commit,} & \text{if } t \text{ exists and the HTTP response is good} \\ \text{ignore,} & \text{if duplication or DNE} \end{cases}$$

In this representation, the piecewise function specifies that the commit action should be taken if the manga with title t exists and the HTTP response is good. On the other hand, the ignore action should be taken if there is duplication or if the manga does not exist (DNE).

2.0.2 Generating sitemap.xml

Let $\mathbb{B}$ be the buffer for the *sitemap.xml* file.

We use a base of $\mathbb{B}$ being

```
<urlset xmlns="http://www.sitemaps.org/schemas
  ↪ /sitemap/0.9">
...
</urlset>
```

On the inside of the *urlset* we iterate the URLs in tags such as ...

```
<url>
  <loc>https://manga.adgstudios.co.za</loc>
</url>
...
...
<url>
  <loc>https://manga.adgstudios.co.za/manga/
    ↪ manga1</loc>
</url>
...
<url>
  <loc>https://manga.adgstudios.co.za/manga/
    ↪ manga1</loc>
</url>
...
<url>
  <loc>https://manga.adgstudios.co.za/manga/
    ↪ manga2</loc>
</url>
```

In pseudo code

Let B be the buffer for the sitemap.xml file.

Set B as the base:

B = '<urlset_xmlns="http://www.sitemaps.org/

```
↪ schemas/sitemap/0.9">\n'
```

Iterate over the URLs:

For each url in the list of URLs:

Add the url to the buffer B:

```
B += '\n<url>\n'
```

```
B += '\n\n<loc>' + url + '</loc>\n'
```

```
B += '\n</url>\n'
```

Add the closing tag to the buffer B:

```
B += '</urlset>\n'
```

2.0.3 Setting up Route for sitemap.xml

In our website endpoint. */sitemap.xml* we follow this process

- Select all the URL data from the database
- Generate our sitemap.xml file
- Render the sitemap.xml on the website

Basically that is it!

2.0.4 Submit your sitemaps.xml to the Search Engines

Now you basically tell the search engines to pull your sitemap.xml using the given URL you have engineered.

2.0.5 Architecture for this process and manga.adgstudios.co.za real world example

Figure 2.1: Architecture